

Impact of the British Capital Investment during Indian National Movement (1915-1939)

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Abstract :

Undoubtedly, the Indian National Movement was not only a movement for freedom at expression, freedom of the press, freedom of organization and political freedom, but there are also a movement against the attack on the Indian economy by the British rule. The freedom struggle was also a struggle for economic development with the passage of time, economic ideology also developed among the people from the very beginning the movement took the stand of favor of the poor.

An attempt was made to give a socialist outlook to the movement brought a change in the direction of programs at agricultural reforms.

In fact the freedom struggle was basically the result of a fundamental contradiction between the interest of the Indian people and British colonialism. It was additionally notable and multi-class movement for Indians, during the colonial period, it was seen that the Indian economy was rapidly slipping back and the country was going through a period of under development.

The voice against the economy in India was raised in the late nineteenth century. The current article highlights the impact of the British Capital Investment during Indian National Movement.

Keywords : Capital, investment, national movement, contradiction.

Introduction :

Impact of the British Capital Investment during Indian National Movement (1915-1939) is an article which briefs the linkage of the Indian National Movement with organization which were against the Britain. The first illustration in this regards has been made about the Indian emigres who went to foreign countries in the early decade of twentieth century and attempt to procure arms and money to assist the liberation among them there revolutionaries who went to America, Canada, Argentina, France, Germany, China, Verma, Philippines, etc. After October revolution the shifted to Russia. The article has explained the early efforts of there revolutionaries to have these contacts with the Russian Government and its leader Lenin.

This article has given an account of the works done by the worker's welfare league, which submitted memorandum with details about the miseries and pasteurization of Indian people under the British rule to the joint parliamentary committee and to Montague. The article also mention the action of the provisional government of Hindustan at Kabul, the discussion an India in the second conference of the Communist International.

When the non Co-operation movement was unconditionally withdrawn there were world wide reaction on it. The article has given specific mention of the memorandum submitted to constitute a labour party in India. When the non co-operation movement was withdrawn unconditionally. In its solidarity with the Chinese revolution the Indian National Movement apposed the British government its action of sending the Indian army to repress the revolution in China.

The another international linkage that has found place in the article is India's association with the league against imperialism, some details about the league's conference held at Brussels and attended by Jawahar Lal Nehru. The league against imperialism also made efforts to organize public government by starting Meerut conspiracy case.

The article has also incorporated the attempts made by the various congresses at the C.I. to guide and enthuse the liberation movement in India. The article has thus explained as how the Indian Liberation Movement was fought as an irreversible part at the World revolutionary process.

In general concept of imperialism the stage of finance capital has been marked as export of capital to other countries for exploitation of the cheap human and material resources by the installation of industrial complexes under the fostering care of imperialist capital. But the analysis of this fact in relation to India it becomes evidently clear that the capital that was exported from England to India never exceeded more than what was exported or drained from India to England. The chief modes through which the Indian capital was drained out from India to England, were tributes, home-charges, salaries and pension of the British officials profits and dividends of British companies, etc.

Secondly, the capital which came to India from England was not a willful investment to extract Indian resources rather under the economic compulsion of Britain. As, during and after the first World War the war born economic crisis, on which account the Indian market was shrinking from the control of England and was occupied by the Japanese and American goods, England had to protect it. In such an inner imperialist market rivalry as appeared in the period several measures, including protective tariff to capital investment, were applied by the colonial rulers. With the application of this strategy simultaneous transformed the British exploitative mechanism into a more developed form of exploitation. The programme of boycott and Swadeshi adopted by the Indian National Movement were a type of anti-dota to encounter this offensive of the British imperialism. The demands for providing more amenities to Indian industries was also a strategy of the Indian National Movement. The perusal of the entire national movement shows that each time when the national movement approached a tormented phase it was withdrawn or suspended for economic concessions from imperialist rule. Every time the leading political force, the Indian National Congress, compromised with imperialism for certain economic concessions and when the contradiction between the Indian and the British capital sharpened the congress led mass movement to pressurize imperialism under the mass movement and to lean to extend certain concessions to Indian capital. This shows irreconcilability between the interests of India and England. The industrial

growth in India in certain sectors like textile, etc. was not the resultant effects of the capital exported to India from England rather the pros and cons of the struggle fought by the national movement through its strategy of boycott and Swadeshi.

Conclusion :

The article has explained with special reference at the efforts done by the British Government. In its general conclusion the article has inferred the Indian National Movement as a part and parcel of the world anti-colonial movement fought by the co-operation and assistance of the forces at the world revolutionary process. It could be said that Britain was reducing India to the circumstance with a monetary repayment, a wellspring of raw port for British ventures, a business opportunity for British produces. In this article Britisher's began to comprehend that since pioneer control of the Indian economy continued.

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